

Market Recommender System using machine learning by applying Stochastic gradient descent method

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Abstract—The insurance broking, mainly driven by suggesting the right market/carrier for the product where the client would like to cover for, by carefully making calculus on their history of data (like placements, bind, quotes and its ratios., etc) these calculations help to evaluate the suggested market is the right fit for the client and it increased client retention (renewals). However, the current system may not a primitive enough to handle this case. This paper intended to analyze various machine learning algorithms to check if it has a primitive role in this area and to analyze how much the side data influences on deciding the scores.

some of domain expertise. In this model we have done a test sample data to manipulate the scenario with key elements from insurance broking world such as number of submissions and number of quotes against the product (the product for which client want to insured against or wanting the risk to be covered).

To test the hypothesis, the following data sets are used (in summary)

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional system uses historical data along with brokers knowledge to suggest market which requires immense re-sourcing and hard to automate. This paper to understand how recommender systems could help to ease this process and also, we would be evaluating various models of the recommender. The common key challenges faced in this area are

- History data doesnt provide value for the new products
- Lack of missing key information form tapped systems
- Combination of product and create a scarcity of data
- Predicting the right carrier based on given information would require a mathematical approach.

These challenges are the right, fit for the data science/machine learning.

In this paper, we are intended to evaluate Stochastic gradient descent method to find the market suggestion by supplying supporting data in factorization recommender. We also evaluate this with other models to cross apply the score and to prove our hypothesis. The other models are namely

- Popularity recommender
- Factorization recommender
- similarity recommender

The common approach for the machine learning consists of following steps

- 1.Data Preparation → 2. Choosing model
- 3. Build Model and Train model using test samples
- 4.Evaluate and → 5. Deploy

II. DATA PREPARATION

Data preparation is the most crucial part of any data science problem. It would take about 60% of time and would require

Fig. 1. "distribution of values from MScore"

We have used 33% of null score to test the model 2, as in most of the real-world scenario the scores may not be available upfront for us to make the recommendation if In case of any new market products.

```
Number_Ratings = float(len(data))
Number_Product = float(len(np.unique(data["Carrier_id"])))
Number_Users = float(len(np.unique(data["Client_id"])))
Sparsity = (Number_Ratings/(Number_Product*Number_Users))*100.0
print "Sparsity of Dataset is", Sparsity, "Percent"
```

Sparsity of Dataset is 5.73593073593 Percent

Fig. 2. "Data sparsity"

Data sparsity was calculated as 5.7% which is the right fit for us to train and test the model.

III. CHOOSING THE MODEL

Based on the given data we have chosen factorization model to test our hypothesis. Factorization Recommender trains a model and capable of predicting a score for each possible combination of users and items. The internal coefficients of the model are learned from known scores of users and items. Recommendations are then based on these scores. We assumed in our hypothesis that the initial score is available in data, this score may not be available handy in many cases and we could generate using the model.

The factor terms model interactions between users and items.

For example, if a user ie customer wants to make risk cover for a specific product, the factor terms attempt to capture that, causing the model to predict lower scores for other product for which customer is not intended to and higher scores for intended product. And factorization machine assigns weighted average for those based on terms available in user data.

This also helps in other problem where broker face this in real world situation. Say if broker wants to recommend an additional product which client may be interested to insure/cover. This could be done by finding similar clients and their patterns using calculated weights .1.

More formally, when side data is not present, the predicted score for user i on item j is given by

$$score(i, j) = \mu + \omega_i + \omega_j + a^T x_i + b^T y_j + u_i^T v_j \quad (1)$$

where μ is a global bias term, ω_i is the weight term for user i, ω_j is the weight term for item j, x_i and y_j are respectively the user and item side feature vectors, and a and b are respectively the weight vectors for those side features such as number of submission, number of quote, submission ratio, quoted ratio, marketscore, count of placement..etc. The latent factors, which are vectors of length num factors, are given by u_i and v_j . When binary target = True, the above score is passed through a logistic function 2:

$$Score(i, j) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-z)} \quad (2)$$

where z is the original linear score.

In stochastic, gradient descent 3, the true gradient of $Q(\omega)$ is approximated by a gradient at a single example:

$$\omega := \omega - \tilde{h} \nabla Q_i(\omega) \quad (3)$$

IV. TRAIN MODEL USING TEST SAMPLES

To optimize the objective function 4

$$\min_{w,a,b,v,u} \frac{1}{|D|} \sum_{i,j,r_{ij} \in D} \lambda(score(i, j), r_{ij}) + \lambda_a + \lambda_b \quad (4)$$

where

$$\lambda_a = \lambda_1 (\|W\|_2^2 + \|a\|_2^2 + \|b\|_2^2)$$

$$\lambda_b = \lambda_2 (\|U\|_2^2 + \|V\|_2^2)$$

and where Dis the observation dataset, r_{ij} is the rating that user gave to item j, $U=(u_1, u_2, \dots)$ $U=(u_1, u_2, \dots)$ denotes the users latent factors and $V=(v_1, v_2, \dots)$ $V=(v_1, v_2, \dots)$ denotes the item latent factors. The loss function is λ by default. λ_1 denotes the linear regularization parameter and λ_2 the regularization parameter.

The model is trained using one of the following solvers known as Stochastic Gradient Descent with additional tricks to improve convergence. To split the training and test data have used 75/25 3 split.

```
sf = graphlab.SFrame(data)
sf_train, sf_test = sf.random_split(.75, seed=5)
print "Train :",len(sf_train), "Test ",len(sf_test) ,"Total" ,(len(sf_train)+len(sf_test))
Train : 48 Test 17 Total 65

sf_train, sf_validate = sf_train.random_split(.75)
```

Fig. 3. "test data split for train and test "

To set a base model for evaluation have created popularity recommender model as a base build, the RMSE calculated as 2.91.4 this would recommend the item based on the popularity.

```
Popularity Recommender

popularity_recommender = graphlab.recommender.popularity_recommender.create(sf_train,
user_id='Client_id',
item_id='Carrier_id',
target='Mscore')

popularity_recommender.evaluate_rmse(sf_test, 'Mscore')

Recsys training: model = popularity

Warning: Ignoring columns Client, Carrier, Product_id, Submission, Quote, item_id, Avg of Mscore;
To use these columns in scoring predictions, use a model that allows the use of additional features.

Preparing data set.
Data has 33 observations with 29 users and 18 items.
Data prepared in: 0.003647s
33 observations to process; with 18 unique items.
```

Fig. 4. "Calculated RMSE "

A. Build 2 : item similarity recommender using jaccard similarity

Have used similarity type as jaccard method 5 and RMSE calculated as 4.74874025419

```
item_similarity_recommender = graphlab.recommender.item_similarity_recommender.create(sf_train,
user_id='Client_id',
item_id='Carrier_id',
target='Mscore',
similarity_type = 'jaccard')

print "Test RMSE on model", item_similarity_recommender.evaluate_rmse(sf_test, 'Mscore')['rmse_overall']

Recsys training: model = item_similarity

Warning: Ignoring columns Client, Carrier, Product_id, Submission, Quote, item_id, Avg of Mscore;
To use these columns in scoring predictions, use a model that allows the use of additional features.

Preparing data set.
Test RMSE on model
Data has 33 observations with 29 users and 18 items.
Data prepared in: 0.005981s
Training model from provided data.
Gathering per-item and per-user statistics.
```

Fig. 5. "jaccard RMSE "

```

item_similarity_recommender = graphlab.recommender.item_similarity_recommender.create(sf_train,
                                                                 user_id='Client_id',
                                                                 item_id='Carrier_id',
                                                                 target='Mscore',
                                                                 similarity_type='cosine')
print "Test RMSE on model", item_similarity_recommender.evaluate_rmse(sf_test, 'Mscore')['rmse_overall']

Recsys training: model = item_similarity
Warning: Ignoring columns Client, Carrier, Product_id, Submission, Quote, item_id, Avg of Mscore;
To use these columns in scoring predictions, use a model that allows the use of additional features.
Preparing data set.
Data has 33 observations with 29 users and 18 items.
Data prepared in: 0.009004s
Test RMSE on model

```

Fig. 6. "cosine RMSE "

B. Build 3 : item similarity recommender using cosine similarity

While using cosine similarity 6 method in factorization recommender the RMSE score is 4.75197387012

C. Build 4 : using factorization recommender

In Factorization recommender its observed that the RMSE score 7 obtained as 0.11 which conclude this the best model for the given data set and problem

```

regularization_terms = [10**-5, 10**-4, 10**-3, 10**-2, 10**-1]
best_regularization_term=0
best_RMSE = np.inf
for regularization_term in regularization_terms:
    factorization_recommender = graphlab.recommender.factorization_recommender.create(sf_train,
                                                                 user_id='Client_id',
                                                                 item_id='Carrier_id',
                                                                 target='Mscore',
                                                                 regularization_term)

    evaluation = factorization_recommender.evaluate_rmse(sf_validate, 'Mscore')
    if evaluation['rmse_overall'] < best_RMSE:
        best_RMSE = evaluation['rmse_overall']
        best_regularization_term = regularization_term
print factorization_recommender.get_num_items_per_user()

Recsys training: model = factorization_recommender
Preparing data set.
Data has 33 observations with 29 users and 18 items.
Data prepared in: 0.012024s
Training factorization_recommender for recommendations.

```

Fig. 7. "factorization recommender RMSE "

V. EVALUATE

Evaluate model ability to make the rating predictions or recommendation which usually done by training the model to predict a particular target, and comparing the used model comparison for root-mean-squared error (RMSE) . Suppose \vec{Y} and Y are vectors of length N , where \vec{Y} contain the actual rating and Y the predicted rating then the RMSE .5 is defined as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\vec{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

With the model build its obvious that the factorization model worked well with the data set and also shown improved performance when we have side data such as Quote, Submission and count of placement to support the predictions.

VI. DEPLOY

The model deployment done by various methods and we could have layers of training model to support the prediction to work better. Typical way is to deploy this as a service for the other layer to consume by accessing this with required

parameters. In our example we have used the turi utility which has ability to show the model output 8 9 in more interactive way.

```

# Create an interactive view
view = model.views.explore(item_data=items, item_name_column='Carrier')
view.show()

View object

URI: http://localhost:32212/view/c04de0b9-7766-4297-8135-1381fe1bd170
HTML:
<gl-recommender-explore
uri="http://localhost:32212/view/a1ae4e44-cc4b-47cd-a6b5-275712e3f483"
api_key=""
/>

```

Fig. 8. "gl Recommender explorer"

Fig. 9. "gl Recommender explorer view"

The utility provide the option to interact with the data and support to find the similar items ie finding similar client who has covered for similar product which client interested in and also this provide the view of recommendable similar items.

A. Similar business case : Decision support system

On other useful business case for the machine learning to use the classification algorithm when we have labeled set of data is available from the source system.

Focus Item				
	Carrier	Item ID		Avg of Mscore
	Wheaton World Wide Moving	15		5
Top Similar Items				
Score	Carrier	Item ID	rank	Avg of Mscore
0.22	Vital Axiom	1	1	2.5714285714285...
0.17	Wolfram Research	18	2	0
0.14	Weather Decision Technologies	20	3	0.8
0.14	WeMakelSafer	4	4	0
0.13	Whitby Group	14	5	0
0.13	Xatori	19	6	7
0.10	Vizzuality	7	7	3.4285714285714...

Fig. 10. "Search Similar items"

Example if Broker has selected a market which is outside of this recommendation and he/she thinks that market is the

INPUT ITEM / USER	
weather	
Items	
Weather Underground	9
Weather Channel	13
Weather Decision Technologies	20
Webitects	21
Weight Watchers	6
Users	
AccuWeather	Avg of Mscore
Aidin	2
Alarm.com	
Amazon Web Services	
3 Round Stones, Inc.	

Fig. 11. "Recommender Similar items"

right fit 10. If we have labels then we could run classification on the data set to classify the selected market has any risk or whether its fit for the selected criteria 11. This would improve the usability of the data and provide additional ability to broker on making decision.

VII. CONCLUSION

In Data science world there is no right or wrong answer. For the given circumstances the assumed hypothesis proved reasonably well and thus shows the machine learning and recommender systems are right fit for the Insurance broking markets for making decision and which would greatly support for business growth and for retention of client with their satisfactions.

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